

Pruned-ADAPT-VQE: compacting molecular ansätze by removing irrelevant operators

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Abstract

The adaptive derivative-assembled pseudo-Trotter variational quantum eigensolver (ADAPT-VQE) is one of the most widely used algorithms for electronic structure calculations. It adaptively selects operators based on their gradient, constructing ansätze that continuously evolve to match the energy landscape, helping avoid local traps and barren plateaus. However, this flexibility in reoptimization can lead to the inclusion of redundant or inefficient operators that have almost zero amplitude, barely contributing to the ansatz. We identify three phenomena responsible for the appearance of these operators: poor operator selection, operator reordering, and fading operators. In this work, we propose an automated, cost-free refinement method that removes unnecessary operators from the ansatz without disrupting convergence. Our approach evaluates each operator after ADAPT-VQE optimization by using a function that considers both its amplitude and position in the ansatz, striking a balance between eliminating low-amplitude operators while preserving the natural reduction of coefficients as the ansatz

grows. Additionally, a dynamic threshold based on the amplitudes of recent operators enables efficient convergence. We apply this method to several molecular systems and find that it reduces ansatz size and accelerates convergence, particularly in cases with flat energy landscapes. The refinement process incurs no additional computational cost and consistently improves or maintains ADAPT-VQE performance.

1 Introduction

Quantum simulation has long been regarded as one of the most promising applications of quantum computing, with the potential to achieve a significant quantum advantage.^{1,2} Early quantum simulations were performed using the Phase Estimation Algorithm (PEA).³ However, PEA requires deep quantum circuits and extensive use of controlled operations, making it impractical for near-term quantum devices. As an alternative, the Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE)^{4,5} was introduced, better suited for the Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) era.^{6,7} Despite its advantages, VQE still faces several challenges, including susceptibility to local traps^{8,9} and barren plateaus,^{10,11} which can hinder optimization and convergence.

The effectiveness of VQE strongly depends on the choice of ansatz. An ideal ansatz should be expressive enough to capture the exact solution while remaining shallow enough to be implemented within the coherence time of current quantum hardware. Additionally, it should have a minimal number of parameters to ensure efficient optimization and avoid unnecessary complexity in the classical optimization process. In molecular simulations, chemically inspired ansätze, such as Unitary Coupled-Cluster (UCC) methods,^{12,13} are commonly used. These ansätze encode fermionic excitations applied to an initial state, such as Hartree-Fock. However, the direct encoding of fermionic excitations leads to deep circuits with a large number of two-qubit gates, making them impractical for NISQ devices.¹⁴

To address these limitations, adaptive derivative-assembled pseudo-Trotter VQE (ADAPT-VQE)¹⁵ was introduced as an iterative and problem-tailored approach. Instead of defining a fixed ansatz, ADAPT-VQE constructs the wavefunction dynamically by adding one fermionic excitation per iteration, selecting only the most relevant operators required for convergence. This adaptive strategy significantly reduces circuit depth compared to conventional VQE while ensuring that the ansatz remains compact and efficient. The resulting wavefunction

takes the form:

$$|\Psi\rangle = \prod_{i=1}^N e^{\theta_i \hat{A}_i} |\psi_0\rangle \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of selected excitation operators ($\{\hat{A}_i\}$). Unlike standard UCC-based VQE, where all parameters θ_i are optimized simultaneously, ADAPT-VQE optimizes the ansatz incrementally. Moreover, by reusing parameters from previous iterations, ADAPT-VQE improves convergence and mitigates local traps.¹⁶ This iterative refinement provides a warm start for parameterized circuits, a strategy demonstrated to be key in enhancing the efficiency of variational algorithms.¹⁷

Despite its advantages, ADAPT-VQE faces significant challenges on current quantum hardware. The algorithm’s iterative nature still leads to deep quantum circuits, exceeding the feasible execution depth of today’s devices. Also, high noise levels from gate errors, read-out inaccuracies, and crosstalk degrade result accuracy.¹⁸ Moreover, mitigation methods add computational overhead, further limiting ourselves to the simplest techniques.¹⁹ Thus, while ADAPT-VQE remains a powerful algorithm, its practical application to significant molecular systems is currently infeasible due to circuit depth, amount of measurements, noise, and hardware constraints, requiring significant advancements in quantum technology.²⁰ Further algorithmic improvements aimed at reducing circuit depth are essential to enable its implementation on near-term quantum devices.^{21–24}

The ADAPT-VQE method relies on the optimal selection of a new excitation operator at each iteration. Typically, this selection is based on the operator with the largest gradient, as this approach has been shown to mitigate optimization issues caused by barren plateaus.¹⁶ However, the gradient-based criterion is not infallible. The operator with the highest gradient does not always lead to the greatest energy reduction, and in some cases, its contribution to the energy can be negligible, with a nearly vanishing amplitude.²⁵ Since such situations cannot be anticipated in advance, the gradient-driven, one-operator-at-a-time ansatz construction remains the most effective strategy currently available in ADAPT-VQE.

This study has two main objectives: (i) to identify and understand scenarios where certain

excitation operators appear to perform poorly, exhibiting nearly zero amplitude, and (ii) to develop an efficient strategy for eliminating these redundant operators, thereby constructing more compact ansätze that yield shorter quantum circuits without compromising energy accuracy.

2 Spotting superfluous operators

To begin, we aim to characterize cases where certain excitation operators contribute negligibly to the ansatz energy, exhibiting nearly zero amplitudes. To illustrate this issue, we investigate the performance of ADAPT-VQE in a stretched linear H_4 system (interatomic distance of 3.0 Å). Highly correlated systems like this are particularly challenging, often requiring long ansätze to achieve chemical accuracy. For our simulations, we employ the 3-21G basis set, consisting of 8 orbitals (Figure ??) mapped to 16 qubits. The transformation from Fermionic to spin operators is performed using the Jordan–Wigner mapping.²⁶ The excitation operator pool consists of UCC operators restricted to occupied-to-virtual spin-singlet adapted single and double excitations.¹⁵ We denote these operators as \hat{A}_i^a and \hat{A}_{ij}^{ab} for single and double excitations, respectively, where i, j represent the occupied orbitals in the Hartree-Fock determinant ($1a_g$ and $1a_u$), and a, b span all virtual orbitals. For simplicity, the notation na_g and na_u ($n = 1, 4$) is abbreviated as ng and nu , respectively. Explicit expressions for the spin-adapted unitary fermionic operators in terms of creation and annihilation operators can be found in the Supporting Information (Section ??). Numerical optimization of amplitudes is carried out using the Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno algorithm.²⁷ Simulations are conducted with an in-house Python implementation of ADAPT-VQE, utilizing the NumPy,²⁸ SciPy,²⁹ and OpenFermion³⁰ packages.

Figure 1a illustrates the evolution of the energy error in ADAPT-VQE relative to full configuration interaction (FCI) as a function of the number of operators in the ansatz. The distribution of absolute amplitudes at $N = 69$ (Figure 1b) reveals the presence of

several operators with nearly zero amplitudes. Notably, contiguous operators with negligible amplitudes correspond to flat regions in the energy profile, indicating that, despite being selected based on the gradient criterion, these operators do not meaningfully contribute to energy optimization.

Figure 1: (a) Energy error (in a.u.) of the ADAPT-VQE with respect to FCI as a function of the number of operators, and (b) distribution of absolute amplitudes at $N = 69$ obtained for linear H_4 with interatomic distance of 3.0 \AA , with the 3-21G basis set. Vertical dashed red lines delimit flat energy regions.

A detailed analysis of the occurrence of operators with $\theta \approx 0$ in the ADAPT-VQE ansatz reveals three underlying mechanisms: (i) poor or incorrect operator selection, (ii) operator reordering, and (iii) fading operators.

2.1 Poor operator selection

Typically, after adding a new operator and re-optimizing all amplitudes, using the previously optimized values as initial guesses in the classical optimization (a technique known as amplitude recycling), the ansatz gains expressivity, leading to a lower energy and reduced error relative to the exact solution. However, in some cases, the newly added operator \hat{A}_N has little to no impact on the ansatz, resulting in a nearly zero amplitude $\theta_N \approx 0$ from the moment it is introduced, and failing to significantly alter the energy. We classify these instances as a consequence of poor (or incorrect) operator selection.

As illustrated in Figure 2, certain operators exhibit nearly zero amplitudes immediately after being introduced into the ansatz, indicating that their selection did not meaningfully contribute to the optimization process.

Figure 2: Amplitude values of various operators from their introduction to iteration 34 for the simulation of linear H_4 with interatomic distance of 3.0 \AA , with the 3-21G basis set. Cross markers indicate when the operator is removed by Pruned-ADAPT-VQE (see Section 4).

These operators exhibit consistently small amplitudes from the moment they are introduced, remaining negligible throughout the entire simulation. This suggests that they were poorly or incorrectly selected and could potentially be removed from the ansatz without significant impact. To verify this, we compare the ADAPT-VQE energy at iteration 27

(just after the energy drop observed in Figure 1) with the energy obtained after eliminating these operators, \hat{A}_{1g1g}^{4u4u} and $\hat{A}'_{1g1u}{}^{4g4u}$, and reoptimizing the remaining amplitudes. The resulting energy difference is minimal, approximately 0.046 mHa, reinforcing the need to develop strategies for identifying and eliminating inefficient operators.

2.2 Operator reordering

The adaptive nature of ADAPT-VQE allows the ansatz to dynamically adjust to the specific requirements of the problem being studied. As the wavefunction is iteratively constructed by adding excitation operators, the ansatz continuously evolves to improve accuracy. Notably, once an operator is added to the ansatz, it remains in the pool and is not removed.¹⁵ This can lead to the inclusion of multiple instances of the same operator. While such redundancy can sometimes be beneficial, we have identified cases where adding a duplicate operator causes a sudden drop in the amplitude of the previously included instance. This behavior serves as a reordering mechanism, highlighting ADAPT-VQE’s ability to dynamically optimize the sequence of operators, an important feature given that different orderings of operators in Trotterized forms of UCC are not equivalent.³¹ However, in these cases, the initially introduced operator becomes redundant, with its amplitude diminishing to near zero. Thus, while it no longer effectively contributes to the final wavefunction, it still increases the circuit depth, adding unnecessary computational overhead.

Figure 3 illustrates this reordering effect, showing the progression of operator \hat{A}_{1g}^{3g} , which has been added four different times. In iteration 23, the second \hat{A}_{1g}^{3g} is added, causing a sudden drop in the first operator amplitude. This situation is repeated in iteration 37, when a third operator is added, causing the second \hat{A}_{1g}^{3g} coefficient to drop to almost zero. This shows how operator \hat{A}_{1g}^{3g} is relocated as the ansatz progresses, until the correct position is found. This suggests that the ansatz dynamically adjusts the sequence of operators, effectively reorganizing them to better optimize the wavefunction construction.

Figure 3: Amplitude values of various operators from their introduction to iteration 80 in the simulation of linear H_4 with interatomic distance of 3.0 Å and the 3-21G basis set. Full circles indicate introduction of another instance of the operator. Cross markers indicate when the operator is removed by Pruned-ADAPT-VQE (see Section 4).

2.3 Fading operators

As the ansatz grows, some operators that initially play a significant role, having sizable amplitudes, gradually become irrelevant. In other words, certain operators that were once crucial for describing the wavefunction eventually contribute little to the final solution. Predicting when such recalibrations will occur is generally challenging. One possible explanation is that the ansatz may initially converge to a local minimum where a given excitation operator is essential. However, as the ansatz expands and explores a larger Hilbert space, the algorithm may transition to a lower-energy minimum where the previously important operator is no longer needed, leading to a near-zero amplitude. Additionally, this fading effect could be linked to the "burrowing into the energy landscape" process,¹⁶ where qualitative changes in the wavefunction structure might render certain operators obsolete. Figure 4 exemplifies this phenomenon, showing how operators \hat{A}_{1g1u}^{2g4u} and \hat{A}_{1g1u}^{4g2u} , introduced in iterations 10 and 11 of ADAPT-VQE, initially carry significant weight but become negligible after iteration 30.

Figure 4: Amplitude values of various operators from their introduction to iteration 34 in the simulation of linear H_4 with interatomic distance of 3.0 Å, with the 3-21G basis set. Cross markers indicate when the operator is removed by Pruned-ADAPT-VQE (see Section 4).

2.4 Cooperative operator action

We observe that, in some cases, newly added operators initially have negligible amplitudes but later become significant contributors to the ansatz. While their inclusion may initially appear to be a poor selection, the addition of subsequent operators can trigger a substantial increase in their amplitudes. This suggests that certain operators, despite their seemingly insignificant impact at first, play a crucial role in unlocking specific regions of the Hilbert space. Their effectiveness emerges only when combined with other operators, highlighting the necessity of collective and cooperative action in the construction of an optimal ansatz.

This phenomenon is clearly illustrated in Figure 5, which depicts the ansatz composition at iterations 26 and 27. These iterations coincide with a sudden energy drop (Figure 1a), demonstrating how the cooperative action of multiple operators can unlock lower-energy solutions that were previously inaccessible.

Figure 5: Absolute amplitude coefficients at iteration 26 (a) and 27 (b) of ADAPT-VQE for the simulation of linear H_4 with interatomic distance of 3.0 Å, with the 3-21G basis set.

Operator \hat{A}_{1u1u}^{2u2u} , in position 26 (and, to a lesser extent, operator \hat{A}_{1u1u}^{2u4u} , in position 25) initially appears with a small amplitude. However, after an additional ADAPT iteration, specifically, upon the introduction of operator \hat{A}_{1g1g}^{2g2g} , in position 27, operator \hat{A}_{1u1u}^{2u2u} becomes one of the most significant contributors to the ansatz. The cooperative effect between operators \hat{A}_{1u1u}^{2u2u} and \hat{A}_{1g1g}^{2g2g} is evident when evaluating the energy without operator \hat{A}_{1u1u}^{2u2u} , which leads to an increase of 6.2 mHa. This energy shift exceeds the threshold for chemical accuracy,³² and is more than two orders of magnitude greater than the change observed when removing the poorly selected operators \hat{A}_{1g1g}^{4u4u} and \hat{A}_{1g1u}^{4g4u} (in positions 19 and 20), as dis-

cussed in Section 2.1. This distinction underscores the difference between truly redundant operators and those that, despite initially having small amplitudes, play a crucial role by collectively unlocking key regions of the Hilbert space.

3 Pruned-ADAPT-VQE algorithm

Motivated by the various mechanisms that introduce ineffective operators into the ADAPT-VQE ansatz, and recognizing the potential for ansatz compaction, leading to shorter circuits without compromising energy accuracy, we develop an automated algorithm to remove these unnecessary contributions. The proposed method systematically eliminates poorly selected operators, those with fading amplitudes, and redundant operators arising from reordering, while preserving operators involved in cooperative interactions. To achieve this, we introduce a simple yet effective routine, which we call Pruned-ADAPT-VQE, designed to reduce the computational overhead of ADAPT-VQE.

We recognize that the criterion for removing the i th operator from the ansatz must take into account both the magnitude of its amplitude θ_i and its position within the ansatz. To formalize this, we introduce a decision factor f_i for each operator, defined as the product of two functions: one dependent on the operator’s amplitude and the other on its position:

$$f_i = F_1(\theta_i)F_2(x_i) \tag{2}$$

where x_i is the relative position of the operator in an ansatz with N operators, given by $x_i = i/N$. This formulation ensures that both small-amplitude operators and those appearing earlier in the ansatz are systematically evaluated for potential removal.

Among the possible functions that assign a larger factor to operators with smaller absolute amplitudes, we select the inverse of the squared amplitude, as it naturally disregards the sign

of θ_i and strongly emphasizes operators with near-zero amplitudes:

$$F_1(\theta_i) = \frac{1}{\theta_i^2} \tag{3}$$

Testing with alternative functions ($|\theta_i^{-n}|$, with $n = 0, 1, 3, 4$) did not yield any noticeable advantage or improvement over the choice in equation 3 (see discussion in Section ?? of the Supporting Information).

Additionally, we prioritize the removal of operators with small amplitudes that appear early in the ansatz. This prevents the elimination of cooperative operators and accounts for the natural decrease in amplitude of newly added operators as the ansatz approaches convergence. To achieve this, we introduce a position-dependent function F_2 that decays exponentially with the operator’s position within the ansatz:

$$F_2(x_i) = e^{-\alpha x_i} \tag{4}$$

where α is a positive parameter controlling the influence of position on the removal criterion. Choosing an appropriate value for α requires balancing competing effects: a very large α would excessively penalize later operators, effectively preventing their removal, while a value approaching zero would make the position irrelevant, potentially eliminating recent additions that still contribute to convergence. Through preliminary testing, we find that when α is too small, proper convergence is not achieved, as the latest operator added is always removed in each iteration due to having the smallest coefficient. To prevent this, the function must assign sufficient relevance to the position. We found that beyond a certain threshold, the method performs well. However, in certain cases, like linear H_4 , using an intermediate α value (≈ 10) provides a reasonable compromise, ensuring effective pruning while maintaining smooth ansatz optimization, which improves the result (see discussion in Section ?? of the Supporting Information). Figure 6 illustrates the set of $\{f_i\}$ values when applied to the final ansatz (with 69 excitation operators) of the linear H_4 molecule. The operator with

the highest factor and selected for potential removal corresponds to operator in position 13, identified as a poorly selected operator and appearing along a flat energy region in Figure 1a.

Figure 6: Absolute amplitudes (blue bars) and decision factor values (orange sticks) for every ansatz operator of the linear H_4 with interatomic distance of 3.0 Å, with the 3-21G basis set.

Therefore, to refine the ADAPT-VQE ansatz, we introduce a filtering process (Algorithm 1) that evaluates operators after each optimization iteration, identifying candidates for removal while preserving essential contributions. The selection criterion compares the amplitude θ_j of the operator with the largest decision factor f_j (equation 2) against a dynamic threshold τ . This approach prioritizes the removal of early-appearing operators with negligibly small amplitudes while retaining recently added operators that may play a cooperative role. To define τ , we use a fraction (0.1) of the average amplitude of the N_L most recently added operators:

$$\tau = \frac{0.1}{N_L} \sum_{i=0}^{N_L-1} |\theta_{N-i}| \quad (5)$$

We examined the dependence of the dynamic threshold on N_L in equation 5, varying N_L from 1 to 10 (see Section ?? of the Supporting Information). Our analysis shows that adjusting this parameter has a mild impact on the final outcome for $2 \leq N_L \leq 10$. Therefore, as a balanced choice, we set $N_L = 4$ for all subsequent analyses.

The removal process is performed after a standard ADAPT-VQE iteration, as outlined

in Algorithm 1, and proceeds without reoptimizing parameters, as the elimination of these low-impact operators has a negligible effect on the ansatz. As a result, this step does not increase the overall computational cost of the algorithm, as the evaluation of the decision factor and dynamic threshold is negligible.

Algorithm 1 Prune-ADAPT-VQE algorithm

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1: Initialize: Choose initial ansatz  $\psi(0)$  and operator pool  $\{\hat{A}_i\}$ 
2: repeat
3:   Compute gradients  $\partial E/\partial\theta_i \forall \hat{A}_i$ 
4:   Select operator  $\hat{A}_k$  with the largest gradient
5:   if  $|\partial E/\partial\theta_k| < \epsilon$  then
6:     Terminate
7:   else
8:     Add  $\hat{A}_k$  to the ansatz and optimize parameters  $\theta$ 
9:   end if
10:  Compute  $f_i \forall \hat{A}_i \in \text{ansatz}$  ▷ equation 2
11:  Select operator  $\hat{A}_j$  with largest  $f_j$ 
12:  Compute threshold  $\tau$  ▷ equation 5
13:  if  $\theta_j < \tau$  then
14:    Remove operator  $\hat{A}_j$ 
15:  end if
16:  Compute energy  $\langle \psi(\theta) | \hat{H} | \psi(\theta) \rangle$ 
17: until Convergence
18: Output: Optimized ansatz and energy

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4 Performance of Prune-ADAPT-VQE

Figure 7a compares the performance of Prune-ADAPT-VQE against standard ADAPT-VQE in the simulation of linear H_4 . Without pruning, approximately 35 operators are needed to achieve chemical accuracy, whereas the refinement method reduces this number to 26. Initially, both approaches follow the same energy error profile. The pruning mechanism becomes active just after the flat energy region, around the 26th ADAPT iteration, ensuring that only non-cooperative, unnecessary operators are removed while maintaining accuracy.

Figure 7: (a) Energy errors (in Hartree) with respect to FCI and (b) absolute amplitudes for the $N = 69$ ansatz obtained with ADAPT-VQE (blue) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE (orange) for the linear H_4 system with interatomic distance of 3.0 \AA and with the 3-21G basis set.

The ansatz reduction achieved through operator removal becomes evident when comparing the amplitude distributions of Prune-ADAPT-VQE and standard ADAPT-VQE (Figure 7b). The elimination of irrelevant operators leads to a more compact ansatz. Our pruning strategy appears to be conservative, as several operators with near-zero amplitudes remain. Adjusting the parameters that define the decision factor (equation 2) and the dynamic threshold (equation 5) could enable further (or more restrained) ansatz simplification, depending on computational constraints and accuracy requirements.

A closer examination of the operators removed throughout the Prune-ADAPT-VQE iterations reveals distinct cases within the category of small-amplitude operators. The pruning strategy successfully eliminates wrongly selected excitations, such as operators \hat{A}_{1g1g}^{4u4u} and

$\hat{A}'_{1g1u}{}^{4g4u}$ (Figure 2), as well as fading operators like $\hat{A}_{1g1u}{}^{2g4u}$ and $\hat{A}_{1g1u}{}^{4g2u}$ (Figure 4). Additionally, it removes redundant operators arising from reordering, such as operator $\hat{A}_{1g}{}^{3g}$, which was removed and reincerted several times before finding its optimal position (Figure 3). Conversely, the algorithm effectively identifies and preserves cooperative operators, such as $\hat{A}_{1u1u}{}^{2u2u}$ (Figure 5), ensuring that essential contributions to the ansatz remain intact.

Similar results, demonstrating a reduction in the number of fermionic operators without any loss of accuracy, have been observed in simulations of other molecular ground states. This includes the stretched H_2O molecule (Figure 8a) as well as the square and tetrahedral H_4 models (Figures ?? and ??). As seen in the case of linear H_4 , ansatz reductions due to operator pruning tend to occur after flat energy regions in the ADAPT iterations.

Figure 8: Energy errors (in Hartree) with respect to FCI obtained with ADAPT-VQE (solid blue) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE (dashed orange) ansätze for the (a) H_2O with 3.0 Å O–H distance and computed in the 3-21G basis set with active space of 9 orbitals and one frozen orbital, and (b) N_2 with interatomic distance of 2.0 Å, and computed with the 3-21G basis set with 10 active orbitals.

However, in some cases, Prune-ADAPT-VQE does not provide a significant advantage over the standard ADAPT ansatz growth. For instance, when computing the ground-state energy of N_2 , Prune-ADAPT-VQE follows nearly the same convergence profile as ADAPT-VQE (Figure 8b). Additional comparisons of Prune-ADAPT-VQE and ADAPT-VQE performance can be found in the Supporting Information (Figures ??-??). Notably, even in cases where operator pruning does not yield substantial ansatz reductions, the removal of excitation operators using the proposed approach never compromises the accuracy achieved by ADAPT-VQE.

5 Conclusions

The adaptive nature of ADAPT-VQE allows the ansatz to iteratively evolve, refining itself to better capture the problem landscape as the algorithm progresses. While the gradient-driven approach for ansatz growth offers a clear advantage over other strategies, it is not infallible. In some cases, the wavefunction may contain non-contributing operators, those with near-zero amplitudes, which unnecessarily increase circuit depth without improving accuracy. In this work, we have identified three distinct mechanisms responsible for the presence of such redundant operators: (i) suboptimal operator selection due to limitations in the gradient criterion, (ii) operator reordering effects, where previously selected operators are reintroduced while the amplitudes of their earlier instances diminish, leading to unnecessary redundancy in the ansatz, and (iii) fading operators, which become irrelevant as the ansatz evolves. Recognizing and addressing these issues enables the simplification and compression of ADAPT-VQE ansätze, leading to shorter quantum circuits without compromising accuracy. To achieve this, we propose and implement an automated, cost-free method for pruning redundant operators from the ansatz. Our approach systematically evaluates all ansatz operators after each optimization step, using a function that accounts for both operator position and amplitude. This strategy removes operators with minimal contributions while preserving those that may have cooperative effects in future iterations. By integrating this selection function with a dynamic threshold, adapted based on the amplitudes of recently added operators, we effectively eliminate redundancies while ensuring algorithmic convergence. We validated this approach by computing the ground-state energies of several molecular systems. Our results demonstrate that this method systematically improves ADAPT-VQE simulations, particularly in cases where energy remains constant over extended iterations. While in some instances the method does not lead to significant improvements, it consistently performs at least as well as standard ADAPT-VQE. Given its benefits in reducing ansatz complexity without introducing additional computational overhead, we propose that this pruning strategy be systematically incorporated into ADAPT-VQE to enhance its

efficiency and scalability.

Data Availability Statement

The data that supports the findings of this study are available within the article and its supplementary material.

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Supporting Information Available

In the supportive information section further details about the theory and methodology are provided. These include the definition of the notation of the fermionic excitations in the pool (SI.1) and a description of the molecular orbitals of linear H_4 (SI.2). Also, details of both $F_1(\theta_i)$ (SI.3) and $F_2(x_i)$ (SI.4) functions, part of the decision factor, are provided, as well as from the dynamical threshold (SI.5). Finally, a demonstration of Prune-ADAPT-VQE performance tested on a bunch of molecules is given (SI.6).

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Supporting Information:

Pruned-ADAPT-VQE: compacting molecular ansätze by removing irrelevant operators

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1 Excitation operators in the pool

Each individual excitation operator in the pool consists of a UCC operator restricted to occupied-to-virtual spin-singlet adapted single and double excitations. Occupied (virtual) orbitals in the HF determinant are indicated with i, j (a, b) indices. Single and double excitations take the form:

$$\hat{A}_i^a = \frac{1}{2} [\hat{\tau}_i^a + \hat{\tau}_i^{\bar{a}} - \text{h.c.}] \quad (\text{S1})$$

$$\hat{A}_{ii}^{aa} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\hat{\tau}_{ii}^{a\bar{a}} - \text{h.c.}] \quad (\text{S2})$$

$$\hat{A}_{ii}^{ab} = \frac{1}{2} [\hat{\tau}_{ii}^{a\bar{b}} + \hat{\tau}_{ii}^{\bar{a}b} - \text{h.c.}] \quad (\text{S3})$$

$$\hat{A}_{ij}^{aa} = \frac{1}{2} [\hat{\tau}_{ij}^{a\bar{a}} + \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{\bar{a}a} - \text{h.c.}] \quad (\text{S4})$$

$$\hat{A}_{ij}^{ab} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} [2(\hat{\tau}_{ij}^{ab} + \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{\bar{a}\bar{b}}) + \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{a\bar{b}} + \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{\bar{a}b} + \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{a\bar{a}} + \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{\bar{a}b} - \text{h.c.}] \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$\hat{A}'_{ij}{}^{ab} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} [\hat{\tau}_{ij}^{a\bar{b}} + \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{\bar{a}b} - \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{a\bar{a}} - \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{\bar{a}b} - \text{h.c.}] \quad (\text{S6})$$

$$(\text{S7})$$

where h.c. indicates hermitian conjugate, the bar over orbital indices refer to β -spin orbitals, and $\hat{\tau}_i^a$ and $\hat{\tau}_{ij}^{ab}$ are expressed in terms of creation and annihilation operators as:

$$\hat{\tau}_i^a = \hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_i \quad (\text{S8})$$

$$\hat{\tau}_{ij}^{ab} = \hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_b^\dagger \hat{a}_j \hat{a}_i \quad (\text{S9})$$

2 Molecular orbitals of H_4

Figure S1: Molecular orbitals computed at the HF/3-31G level of linear H_4 with 3.0 Å intermolecular separation

3 Alternative functions for $F_1(\theta_i)$

The objective is to account for the amplitude of each operator, prioritizing those with the smallest contributions. In this section, several values of n ($n = 0, 1, 3, 4$) in equation S10 have been tested.

$$F_1(\theta_i) = \frac{1}{|\theta_i^{-n}|} \quad (\text{S10})$$

Each value of n represents a different weight assigned to the amplitude within the total function.

θ_i^{-0} means that no weight is assigned to the amplitude, giving no preference to operators with small coefficients. This function is expected to yield the same result as ADAPT-VQE. On the other hand, θ_i^{-4} assigns a very high weight to the amplitude. While the

position is still considered, the influence of the amplitude becomes dominant, leading to the selection of operators with the smallest coefficients over those in earlier positions. Since operator amplitudes tend to decrease as the simulation progresses, this would result in the last operator being repeatedly selected, preventing the simulation from converging (see $n = 4$ in S2 and $n = 3, 4$ in S3, S4).

Figure S2: Energy error (in Hartree) with respect to FCI of ADAPT-VQE (black dotted line) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE with different amplitude weights for the linear H_4 with interatomic distance of 3 \AA , and computed with the 3-21G basis set and an active space of 8 orbitals. The triangle indicates where the simulation ended.

Figure S3: Energy error (in Hartree) with respect to FCI of ADAPT-VQE (black dotted line) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE with different amplitude weights for the tetrahedral H_4 with interatomic distance of 3 \AA , and computed with the 3-21G basis set and an active space of 8 orbitals. The triangle indicates where the simulation ended.

Figure S5: Energy error (in Hartree) with respect to FCI of ADAPT-VQE (black dotted line) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE with different α values for the linear H_4 with interatomic distance of 3 Å, and computed with the 3-21G basis set and an active space of 8 orbitals. The triangle indicates where the simulation ended.

Figure S6: Energy error (in Hartree) with respect to FCI of ADAPT-VQE (black dotted line) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE with different α values for the tetrahedral H_4 with interatomic distance of 3 Å, and computed with the 3-21G basis set and an active space of 8 orbitals. The triangle indicates where the simulation ended.

Figure S7: Energy error (in Hartree) with respect to FCI of ADAPT-VQE (black dotted line) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE with α values weights for the H_2O molecule with 3 Å O–H distance, and computed with the 3-21G basis set with active space of 9 orbitals and one frozen orbital. The triangle indicates where the simulation ended.

5 Threshold analysis

Once an operator is selected using the decision factor, we must determine whether to remove it based on a threshold. As the simulation progresses, amplitudes tend to decrease, so operators with smaller coefficients must be allowed into the ansatz, this is taken into account with a dynamic threshold. Equation S12 shows that the threshold value depends on the coefficients of the most N recently added operators in the ansatz.

$$\tau = \frac{0.1}{N_L} \sum_{i=0}^{N_L-1} |\theta_{N-i}| \quad (\text{S12})$$

This adaptive approach facilitates convergence, as the decreasing coefficients lead to a progressively lower threshold, resulting in fewer operators being removed over time. Additionally, it enables the elimination of operators in flat regions, where subsequent operators tend to have larger amplitudes, causing the threshold to rise. Several tests have been conducted, considering the last N operators, with N ranging from 1 to 10.

Figure S8: Energy error (in Hartree) with respect to FCI of ADAPT-VQE (black dotted line) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE with different N values for the linear H_4 with interatomic distance of 3 \AA , and computed with the 3-21G basis set and an active space of 8 orbitals. The triangle indicates where the simulation ended.

Figure S9: Energy error (in Hartree) with respect to FCI of ADAPT-VQE (black dotted line) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE with different N values for the tetrahedral H_4 with interatomic distance of 3 \AA , and computed with the 3-21G basis set and an active space of 8 orbitals. The triangle indicates where the simulation ended.

Figure S10: Energy error (in Hartree) with respect to FCI of ADAPT-VQE (black dotted line) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE with N values weights for the H_2O molecule with 3 \AA O–H distance, and computed with the 3-21G basis set with active space of 9 orbitals and one frozen orbital. The triangle indicates where the simulation ended.

6 Performance of Prune-ADAPT-VQE

Figure S11: Energy errors (in Hartree) with respect to FCI obtained with ADAPT-VQE (solid blue) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE (dashed orange) ansätze for the squared H_4 with interatomic distance of 3 \AA , and computed with the 3-21G basis set and an active space of 8 orbitals.

Figure S12: Energy errors (in Hartree) with respect to FCI obtained with ADAPT-VQE (solid blue) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE (dashed orange) ansätze for the tetrahedral H_4 with interatomic distance of 3 Å, and computed with the 3-21G basis set and an active space of 8 orbitals.

Figure S13: Energy errors (in Hartree) with respect to FCI obtained with ADAPT-VQE (solid blue) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE (dashed orange) ansätze for the linear H_6 system with interatomic distance of 3 Å, and computed with the 3-21G basis set and an active space of 8 orbitals.

Figure S14: Energy errors (in Hartree) with respect to FCI obtained with ADAPT-VQE (solid blue) and Prune-ADAPT-VQE (dashed orange) ansätze for the BeH_2 molecule with interatomic distance of 2.5 Å, and computed with the 3-21G basis set and an active space of 9 orbitals with one frozen orbital.